

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Gil****FIRST NAME: Arturo****PROGRAM CODE: DGEP****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice ProPlus

QUIZ: FINAL COURSE ASSESSMENT

1. Choose the citation style presented in Turabian's Manual.

- IEEE.
- Chicago.**¹
- APA (American Psychological Association).
- MLA (Modern Language Association).

2. Which of the following quotations corresponds to the style of the Turabian manual?

- Johnson writes, "the climate change will stop in 50 years."**²
- Johnson writes "the climate change will stop in 50 years."

¹ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th edition, Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 142.

² Turabian et al., 360.

- Johnson writes that, "the climate change will stop in 50 years."
- None of the above.
3. **Which of the following footnote quotation and its footnote superscript number x is correct?**
- "The permanent growth domestic product of the US increases the CO2 emissions." ^{x}** ³
- "The permanent growth domestic product of the US increases the CO2 emissions ^{x} ."
- "The permanent growth domestic product of the US increases the CO2 **emissions**," ^{x} according to Jhonson.
- "The permanent growth domestic product of the US increases the CO2 emissions", and then he explains in more details ^{x} .
4. **According to the Chicago Manual, choose from the following references that correspond to a journal or newspaper.**
- Kelly, John D., and Martha Kaplan. "Ritual Studies." *Annual Review of Research in Anthropology* 19 (1990): 119-50.**⁴
- "Documenting Sources from the World Wide Web." Modern Language Association, 3 February 2000. <http://www.mla.org/style/sources.htm> (February 17, 2000).

³ Turabian et al., 360.

⁴ Laurent Cleenewerck and Gulma Kabiru, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack for Period 1*, 3rd ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 60.

- Arendt, Hannah. *The Human Condition*. 1958. Reprint, Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1998.
- Hemingway, Ernest. "The Big Two-Hearted River." In *The Nick Adams Stories*, edited by Philip Young, 159-180. New York: Bantam Books, 1973.

5. **Select the correct way to write a series of numbers according to the recommendations in the Turabian manual.**

- From 40-50.
- Forty five to fifty.
- From 40 to 50.**⁵
- 40-50.

6. **Regarding the use of semicolons, select the form recommended by the Turabian Manual.**

- Climate change has reduced economic growth; for many countries' economies have even declined.
- Climate change has reduced economic growth; but many countries' economies have even declined.
- Climate change has reduced economic growth; and many countries' economies have even declined.
- Climate change has reduced economic growth; many countries' economies have even declined.**⁶

7. **Choose the UK spelling.**

⁵ Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 337.

⁶ Turabian et al., 311.

- Labor.
- Defence.**⁷
- Defense.
- Color.

8. **Select the qualitative research methodology in which the researcher participates in the community for some time.**

- Ethnography.**⁸
- Ethology.
- Grounded theory.
- Phenomenology.

9. **In qualitative research method, the use of a complex array of data from a variety of sources, using a variety of strategies is termed as:**

- Complex research.
- Data construction.
- Triangulation.**⁹
- None of the above.

10. **The following sentences correspond to a research problem statement. Indicate which is the appropriate order: Topic-**

⁷ European Commission, *English Style Guide*, 8th ed. 2016
https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/styleguide_english_dgt_en.pdf, 77.

⁸ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, Fourth edition (Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019), 112.

⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, 98.

Research question-Significance. A)- To create policies aimed at raising awareness of climate change in industrialized societies. B)- I am studying the difference between the perception of climate change between industrialized and non-industrialized countries. C)- I am looking at how the interests of industrial corporations influence public opinion on climate change.

- B-C-A.¹⁰
- A-B-C.
- A-C-B.
- C-A-B.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019.
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- European Comision, *English Style Guide*, 8th ed. 2016 https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/styleguide_english_dgt_en.pdf.
- Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 8th edition. Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

¹⁰ Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 19.